

ISic3333

Honorific for Marcus Appuleius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cossura

Place of origin (modern)

Pantelleria

Provenance

from cisterns on the acropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Pantelleria, Pantelleria excavation store, inventory 18315, 18316, 814, 18317, 18318

Physical Description

multiple fragments from a marble plaque, originally attached to a statue base

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [M(arco)AppuleioM(arci)f(ilio)Quir(ina)][]
2. [][ad]ecto in V
3. [decuriasabImp(eratore)TraianoOptimoAug(usto)praef(ecto)] coh(ortis) [I]
4. [U]p(iae) Tra[ian]
[(ae)Cugern(orum)c(ivium)R(omanorum)donisdonatoabImp(eratore)Traiano]
5. [Opt]imo Aug(usto) [belloDacico]hastapuraetcorona]
6. trib(un)o mil(itum) leg(ionis) [ITraia]n(ae) fort(is) pr[ae]f[ect]o]alae
[proc(uratori)]
7. Aug(usti) ab ann[on]i]a]adPu]teolos praef(ecto) cla[ssis]Alexandrinae]
8. L(ucius) Appuleius M(arci) f(ilius) Q[uir]i]n]sulanus piissimo p[atri]
faciund(um) curavit]

Apparatus

Text of Schäfer and Alföldy 2015

Translation (en)

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175856

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2005.0678

Alföldy, G. 2005. Ein römischer Ritter aus Cossura (Pantelleria). *Zeitschrift für Papyrologie und Epigraphik*. 151: 193-213.

Schäfer, T., Alföldy, G. 2015. Inschriften von der Akropolis von Pantelleria. In

Schäfer, T., Schmidt, K., Osanna, M.(eds.), *Cossyra I. Die Ergebnisse der Grabungen auf der Akropolis von Pantelleria / S. Teresa. Der Sakralbereich*. Rahden. pp. 777-804. At 785-789 kat.3 abb.32-38

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic3333. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4358205>